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Professional Development of Citizenship Education Teachers and Moral Development of Students in Secondary Grammar Schools in the South West Region of Cameroon

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the influence of professional development of citizenship education teachers on the moral development of students in secondary grammar schools of the South West Region of Cameroon. The sample of the study was made up of 143 citizenship education teachers. Three sampling techniques were used in this study namely; the stratified, purposive and the simple random sampling techniques. The research design used was the sequential explanatory design. The research instruments used were teachers' questionnaire as well as interview guide for Heads of Department for Citizenship Education. The data collected were subjected to descriptive and inferential statistical analysis, using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (S.P.S.S). The major finding of the study was that though there is a relationship between professional development of teachers in Citizenship Education and Moral development of student in Secondary Schools, the relationship was not significant. On the basis of this finding it was recommended that a department for Citizenship Education be introduced in teacher training schools and that there should be an increase in the number of Regional and divisional seminars/workshops for Citizenship Education teachers.

KEYWORDS

Professional Development, Teacher, Citizenship Education and Moral Development.

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Introduction

Professionalism of teachers is a commitment by teachers which ends in quality teaching and learning. The teacher looks at the learners and education as a priority. As such, they enthusiastically accept the challenges of teaching without complain about the learners, the classroom processes and practices. Quality should characterise teachers' interaction with students, administrators and colleagues, parents and the public. With all these, learners and colleagues would be motivated to put forth similar efforts. (Bame, 2007).

Biesta (2011), holds that as teachers undergo more training, it develops their skills and confers the status of professionalism on them. This exercise culminates into a logical high level of responsibility and output as they exercise out their profession. In most countries as indicated by INC Report 1999 there is no specific initial and in-service training of teachers for citizenship education rather many of them are trained but in closely related subject areas. This is also the case of Cameroon. Thus an inadequacy in the preparation of teachers exists not only in the lack of content knowledge but also in their inability to use a range of teaching and learning approaches.

Morality is the value or extent to which an action is right or wrong. Everyone has their own moral code and sense of right and wrong. Morality comprises of an evaluation of what is good and what is bad in absolute terms (Sternbury, 1999). The process of the acquisition of these values is called moral development. Flavel (2003) asserts that moral development is an important ingredient in self-development and the acquisition of values.

Moral development can be taught through Moral Education. Oladipo (2009), asserts that moral education is increasingly becoming a popular topic in disciplines such as psychology and education. He goes further to add that because of increasing media reports of acts of violence, juvenile crime, teenage pregnancy, embezzlement, human rights violation, among others these have made many people to declare that there is a moral crisis, in contemporary society.

According to Piaget (1965), moral development is of prime importance in society. Personal morality is important for personal wellbeing and for our relationship with other fellow humans. Respecting the prevailing moral codes helps make us people of integrity. Moral development can be acquired through parents, school, church, mass media, government agencies, cultural meetings, peer group and the community.

Moral development is taught through citizenship education, in secondary schools in Cameroon. Citizenship Education in Cameroon schools is expected to enhance moral values. Social studies or Citizenship Education equips students with the knowledge, skills and understanding to play an effective role in public life. Through Citizenship Education, students learn about their rights, responsibilities, duties and freedoms and about laws and freedoms, justice and democracy. They learn to take part in decision-making and different forms of actions. Through Citizenship education, students evaluate, make informed judgements and reflect on the consequences of their actions now and in the future (Numfor, 2015).

Statement of the Problem

The teaching of Citizenship education aims at addressing issues relating to social justice, human rights, community cohesion and global interdependence. The importance of citizenship education amongst others include: encouraging students to challenge injustice, inequalities and discrimination, equipping students with the knowledge, skills and understanding to play an effective role in public

life. It also enables students to learn about their rights, responsibilities, duties and freedoms and about laws, justice and democracy. All the above are expected to be seen in our students and youths especially given that citizenship education is now taught in schools. Despite the enormous efforts put in by the Cameroon government in providing schools and Citizenship Education teachers the results at the General Certificate of Education (GCE) have not been very encouraging as revealed by the following GCE results registered; 2016 (52.68%), 2017 (24.67%), 2018 (36.23%), 2019 (53%), and 2020 (46%). We still see a high rate of drug abuse, vandalism, students bullying of teachers (SBT), examination malpractice (fraud), non-respect for school rules and regulations, dishonesty, lack of trust and non-respect for school authorities. These are all indications of low moral development, a situation which keeps educators as well as this researcher very worried. The consequences of this scenario to the society are evident as we can see an increase in the number of crimes, banditry, disrespect of parents and elders by children and younger ones. It is for the above reasons that this study aims at examining the extent to which professional development of citizenship education teachers influences the moral development of students in secondary grammar schools in the South West Region of Cameroon.

Objective of the Study

To find out the relationship between professional development of Citizenship Education teachers and moral development of students.

Research Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between Professional Development of Teachers in Citizenship Education and Moral Development of Students in Secondary Schools.

Theoretical Framework

This study is guided by two theories, Kohlberg's Theory of Moral Development (1958) and the Theory of Reconstructionism of Nziramasanga, (1999).

Kohlberg's Theory of Moral Development (1958)

Lawrence Kohlberg, an American psychologist, extended Piaget's work in cognitive reasoning into adolescence and adulthood. He felt that moral development was a slow process and evolved over time. His six stages of moral development, drafted in 1958, mirrors Piaget's early model. Kohlberg believed that individuals made progress by mastering each stage, one at a time. A person could not skip stages. He also felt that the only way to encourage growth through these stages was by discussion of moral dilemmas and by participation in consensus democracy within small groups. Consensus democracy was rule by agreement of the group, not majority rule. This would stimulate and broaden the thinking of children and adults, allowing them to progress from one stage to another, that is from the basic Preconventional Level (avoiding punishment and getting needs met) through the Conventional Level (broadening the scope of human wants and needs) to the Post-Conventional Level (examining the relative values and opinions of the groups with which they interact).

The significance of this theory lies in the fact that as teachers of Citizenship Education, emphasis should be laid on the characteristics of the learners before teaching them moral developmental skills. In addition to this, the theory supports that, the teaching of Moral Development should be a slow process carried out in stages.

The Theory of Reconstructionism of Nziramasanga, (1999).

The main substance of this theory is that every society is in need of constant reconstruction. To reconstruct is to do something again to make it better. It constitutes the foundation for social change within a dynamic context and involves a reconstruction of education in the process of improving a society (Nziramasanga, 1999). Implied is that the means and ends of education must be completely refashioned to meet the demands of the present day cultural crises. This is also supported by Hatstead and Pike (2008), who opined that “Education must commit itself here and now to the creation of a new social order that will fulfil the basic values of our culture and at the same time harmonize with the underlying social and economic forces of the modern world. “This calls for a radical and fundamental transformation of society through the education of its members to a new shared vision of a common social order. The thrust of the position in the creation of a new mind-set acknowledges that society is always changing and that education should inform the thread for change and practice. Education should be exploited to address social ills bedeviling society thereby creating a better society and worldwide democracy.

As a theory, reconstructionism is very relevant to this study because from many perspectives (moral, economic, political, socio-cultural), Cameroon can be described as a nation in crisis. It is therefore in need of being re-constructed to make it better within an increasing global competitive perspective. This can only be effective through a restructure of content hence a shift from Civics to Citizenship Education.

Literature Review

Professional Development of Citizenship Education Teachers

Teachers are key players in the provision of citizenship education in schools. In their ‘Conclusions on effective teacher education’, European Union (EU) Education Ministers emphasized the major role that teachers have in supporting students develop the knowledge, skills, attitudes and values they need in order to reach their full potential as active members of society. The availability of relevant, high-quality teacher training for citizenship education is an important prerequisite for equipping teachers with the competences they need to fulfill this role. The question that arises therefore, is how top level education authorities address this issue in their regulations and recommendations on initial Teacher Education (ITE), Continuing Professional Development (CPD) and other support measures for teachers and school heads.

The European IEA report of the 2009 ‘International Civic and Citizenship Education’ (ICCS) study (Cobold 2010) showed that teacher confidence in teaching certain topics related to civic and citizenship education was relatively high. On average, across the participating European countries, the majority of teachers felt confident to teach about the constitution and political systems (79%), the EU (78%), and the global community and international organisations (77%). However, other studies have shown the reverse, with several indicating that teachers believe they have not received adequate training to teach citizenship education and, consequently, they lack clear concepts of citizenship, and either do not feel confident to teach it, or feel unsure about choosing the right teaching approaches (Barr et. al. 2015).

There are three essential elements to effective subject teaching: academic and scientific knowledge of the subject matter, pedagogical skills and competences, and an understanding of the social and cultural context of education. Moreover, teachers training should encourage teachers to be reflective and critical with regard to their teaching practice, the management of information and knowledge as well as their interactions with others, especially their students, peers and the local community (Salema, 2005 and 2012).

Teacher training for citizenship education has an added dimension in that the knowledge, skills and competences to be developed by teachers must be firmly based on democratic values and human rights. Crucial to the process is the importance of the personal, ethical and moral development of teachers and the strengthening of their capacity to act as models of active and responsible citizenship. In order to prepare children and young people for active democratic life, teachers of citizenship education need to become ‘carriers and messengers of democratic knowledge, skills and values’ (Mrnjaus, 2012, p.82).

At the same time, it can be argued that teaching in general is a moral activity which seeks to help students develop their personal identity, including their moral and social capacities and their critical reflective abilities (Willemse, et. al., 2015). All teachers, therefore, can be considered responsible for developing their students’ citizenship competences – not just those specialized in the subject or subjects most closely related such as history and social sciences – and all teachers, therefore, should be trained in how to integrate citizenship education into their daily teaching.

The questions that follow from this are: what are the competences needed by teachers citizenship education specialists and teachers of other subjects alike – in order to encourage students to develop the skills necessary to become active, democratic citizens, and what kinds of policies and other support measures are needed to meet teachers’ professional development needs?

Patricia and Thomas (1998) states that the quality of student learning is directly – although not exclusively – related to the quality of classroom teaching. Therefore, the first and most promising way to improve learning is to improve teaching. For quality feedback to be achieved, quality teachers are needed which of course is a problem which citizenship education is currently facing.

Teachers of Citizenship Education are either specialists or generalists depending on the country and level of education. “Specialist teachers” in the context of Citizenship Education, are specialists either in a number of subjects closely related and including Citizenship Education or in a closely related subject. They are not specialists in Citizenship Education per se but may teach it alongside their responsibilities as a teacher of social sciences. This, however, raises the issue of the extent to which these teachers prioritise their Citizenship Education teaching over their other teaching duties. These specialists Citizenship Education teachers also have a background in social science subjects through qualifications and experience, and this may determine where their interest or loyalties lie.

Barr et al (2015) describe professional development as a “career long obligation”. This is so because, when a teacher undertakes a training course, he acquires an insight into the psychological needs of the students. Further, they opine that with a sound professional training, backed by certificates, there will be a corresponding high quality in the use of educational resources in the class.

To motivate and prepare teachers to offer citizenship education program that reflect the qualities needed, pre service and in service training programs should be organized whereby teachers should be seen as beneficiaries and advocates for such programs rather than transmission vehicles (Biesta, 2011) organization of the American study of Education reform. For quality teaching, these training should be systematically integrated with follow-up support and opportunities for sharing.

Biesta (2011) declare that education has an important role in preparing future citizens at all levels of the education system. And so, higher institutions are therefore charged with providing quality teachers who will adapt and develop new approaches that will enable them to engage reflectively and critically with the profound changes within society.

The OECD (1997) suggests that teachers are the final and most important link in the delivery of education as well as the interface through which the objectives of schools and education systems are mediated. Darling-Hammond (2000, 1999) also acknowledges this area of concern and further identifies the critical importance of teaching quality in education provision to meet the challenges presented in today's society.

When teachers receive training, they perceive it to be very useful especially if it forms part of their professional qualification. Geoff (2004) in bringing out the quality of a teacher in the teaching learning process, puts them into two categories that is instructors and facilitators. The instructor is described as one who plans and directs all students' activities so as to transmit a body of knowledge and skills. The teachers are also in charge of assessing and evaluating the students work. This approach leads to learner dependency on teacher and they are unable to solve problems unaided. On the other hand, a facilitators' approach is one in which the teacher helps learners to gain control, plan, carryout and evaluate their learning. The teacher acts as a guide. This makes the learner to be much more committed and interested in their work since it is designed by them.

From the foregoing, Geoff and many effective teachers think a good teacher is the one who uses the facilitator approach. However, quality teaching in practice would be achieved if a continuum between "instructor" and "facilitator" approach is applied by teachers. Thus teachers should move back and forth along this continuum as the situation demands.

Citizenship Education

There exist varied opinions as to what Citizenship Education can contribute in the academic milieu as well as to the development of Cameroon as a whole. Policy makers see it as a means to train youths for intellectual, civic and moral development. They also view it as a means of a smooth integration of youths into the society. To achieve this goal, it will call for conceptualizing and restructuring Civics into Citizenship Education to meet up with current challenges (Cobold, 2010).

An equally valid way of conceptualising approaches is by looking at the aims or goals. Looked at in this way, Citizenship Education comprises three strands; Education about citizenship which focuses on giving learners sufficient knowledge and understanding of national history and the structure and processes of government and political life. Education through Citizenship where learners learn by doing through active participation experiences in and out of school. This reinforces the knowledge component. Education for Citizenship; this encompasses education about and education through citizenship. Here learners are equipped with a set of tools (knowledge and understanding, skills and attitudes, values and dispositions) which enable them to participate actively and sensibly in the roles and responsibilities they encounter in their adult lives. This strand links citizenship education with whole education experience of students (Cobold, 2010).

Social science teachers have their own conception towards citizenship education. This is because they have all been charged with the responsibility to teach Citizenship by the Ministry of Secondary Education (MINESEC) even though they have their respective subject disciplines on which they have been trained. It will be realised that some see it as another extra subject which adds their work load. Others think it is strenuous since the concepts and approaches are not the same as in their trained subject disciplines. Some teachers however, see it as a subject which would impart morals and consequently produce an upright society. They are not only interested in the intellectual capacity but also on producing outstanding citizens and not just intelligent devils. With this in mind, they are likely to offer their all in the instruction of the subject.

Cobold (2010), intimates that, the emphasis on Citizenship Education is an attempt to reinforce those moral values like patriotism, honesty, nationalism, purpose and hard work which he considers are imported values that can effectively fight against some public and private ills like embezzlement, abuse of state property, ethnicity and laziness. He sees it not only as a subject for students but also for young professionals. The subject develops a mindset of general interest, develop national and environmental consciousness, identify and respect the individual and collective rights of citizens. Thus with these positive values, the citizens would be accepted in the society, and they would bring positive contributions to the development of the society through his/her mindset, convictions, beliefs and actions which are positive and oriented towards nation building.

According Hannah H et al (2018), Citizenship Education informs, clarifies, inculcates, promotes, and deepens in Cameroonians and very specially the youths, the essential values of nationhood and good citizenship. They opines that, the subject is intended to prepare and equip the youths for intellectual, patriotic and moral development towards a better social integration. Equally, that it makes the learners to develop an orientation in life that is wholesome and holistic and to be aware of the socio-cultural and political life of their country and to personally appreciate the values of their rights, duties and responsibilities as a member of this Nation. Finally, she sees Citizenship Education as a course that would produce creative and problem solving citizens of high self-esteem and citizens who will be able to handle appropriately their emotional, psychological and intellectual needs. Here, the subject is seen as the ideal course that would make a difference in reshaping our society for the better and breeding a new generation of Cameroonians with a distinct mind-set and with a time love for our country Cameroon.

One of the objectives of citizenship education is to ensure that peace reigns throughout the national territory and beyond even though there are many definitions of the concept (peace). The Cambridge Advanced Learners Dictionary (2005, p. 928) defines peace as freedom from war and violence, especially when people live and work together happily without disagreements. This definition is not tenable because there is hardly any society without disagreements. According to Assefa (1993, p.92),

“peace is a philosophy and in fact a paradigm, with its own values and precepts, which provides a framework to discern, understand, analyse, and regulate all human relationships in order to create an integrated, holistic, and human social order.”

The national syllabus for Citizenship Education for Cameroon schools is designed to incorporate civic and moral education in all candidates. To enable candidates gain knowledge, skills and values which make them informed and active citizens who can engage in their societies. It also makes them aware of their rights, duties and responsibilities thus creating stronger communities for better citizens.

Models of Citizenship Education

There are many models of citizenship education emerging from the research literature. The following prominent ones have been examined in greater detail: the liberal, communitarian, civic republican and critical models.

1. The Liberal Model of Citizenship

The liberal model of citizenship education is often considered the least demanding because citizen involvement in public life is primarily enacted through the vote (Ord, 2003). The model is based on the premise that all citizens have the right to participate in the examination of issues, especially political ones, with the potential to affect them as individuals and groups. The ballot box is often considered and used as one of the strategies to encourage this model of citizenship education.

2. The Communitarian Model of Citizenship

The communitarian model is based on the assumption that a strong sense of community is essential to growth and development of individuals and nations. Consequently, forging a strong sense of community rather than one characterised by individualism is considered very important. Often promoted in this model are values of group membership and particularly the identity and feelings of belonging to a group, and the need to work towards the collective benefit of this group (Ord, 2003). Communitarian ideas have influenced both Christian theology and moral philosophy, and have led to increasing emphasis on the rights and responsibility or duties of individuals to others in their respective communities as well as the need to support structures that build and sustain shared communal values (Willibroad, 2008).

3. The Civic Republican Model of Citizenship

The Civic Republican Model places higher demands on citizens to build and sustain strong democratic processes and institutions. From this perspective, citizens are expected to become the actors of active laws for social change as well as the instruments to prevent corruption (QCA, 1998). Based on Greek and Roman philosophical thought, civic republicanism has emphasized the need for citizens to act politically within the public sphere, and to be actively engaged within a political community as equal and free members. The development of the concept of civic responsibility is often linked to this model. The civic republican approach also highlights the need for citizens to learn civic competences, including the values of “public spiritness, solidarity and the responsibility to act for the common good” (Ofsted, 2002).

4. The Critical Model of Citizenship

This model emanates from various new theories that have expressed inadequacies in existing models of citizenship education QCA (1998). The main argument contained in this model is that an essential responsibility of all citizens is to continuously questioning the existing social order in order to improve it. For example, this can be done by continuously reflecting on pertinent issues and improving societies through social and political actions (Ofsted, 2002). The critical model of citizenship is based on a dynamic view of democracy that is grounded in critical theory. Citizens are supposed to be more engaged in issues that affect them and consequently, for example, be more active in embarking on actions that promote social justice and accountability of both government and international corporations.

Moral Development

Moral development is a universal phenomenon. According to Sterburg (1999), morality comprises of an evaluation of what is good and what is bad in absolute terms. It comprises of praise of what is good and condemnation of what is bad. Morality is thus related to values. Flavel (2003) emphasises that without morality neither the individual within society nor society itself can feel secure to ultimately survive. He further states that the principles that define morality include fairness, justice, the principles of freedom, principles relating to people’s wellbeing and the principle of beauty or aesthetic quality. In addition, Thornburg mentioned that moral development is an important ingredient in self-development and the acquisition of values.

Oladipo (2009) asserts that moral education is increasingly becoming a popular topic in disciplines such as psychology and education. He goes further to add that because of increasing media reports of acts of violence, juvenile crime, teenage pregnancy, embezzlement, human rights violation, among

others, have caused many people to declare a moral crisis, in contemporary society. Though not all of these social concerns are moral in nature, and most have complex origins, there is a growing trend towards linking the solutions to these and related social problems to the teaching of moral and social values in both public and private schools. Moral Education can therefore be described as a component of Citizenship Education. Its aim is to instill right conduct, not only in interpersonal and group social relations, but also in how human beings deal with the whole human race. It is based upon the possession of clear ideals as to what actions are right and what are wrong and the determination of conduct by a constant reference to those ideals.

Moral development focuses on the emergence, change, and understanding of morality from infancy through adulthood. Morality develops across a lifetime and is influenced by an individual's experiences and their behaviour when faced with moral issues through different periods' physical and cognitive development (Oser, 1994).

Moral development is an important part of the socialization process. The term refers to the way people learn what society considered to be "good" and "bad" which is important for a smoothly functioning society. Moral development prevents people from acting on unchecked urges, instead considering what is right for society and good for others. It refers to a certain code of conduct that is derived from one's culture, religion or personal philosophy that guides one's actions, behaviours and thoughts (Arthur, 2003).

According to Banks (2004), in the modern day, empirical research has explored morality through a moral psychology lens by theorists like Sigmund Freud and its relation to cognitive development by theorists like Jean Piaget, Lawrence Kohlberg, B.F. Skinner, Carol Gilligan and Judith Smetana.

The founder of psychoanalysis, Sigmud Freud, proposed the existence of a tension between the needs of society and the individual. According to Freud, moral development proceeds when the individual's selfish desires are repressed and replaced by the values of important socializing agents in one's life (for instance, one's parents).

A proponent of behaviourism, B.F. Skinner similarly focused on socialization as the primary force behind moral development. In contrast to Freud's notion of a struggle between internal and external forces, Skinner focused on the power of external forces (reinforcement contingencies) to shape an individual's development.

Indicators of Moral Development

Abiding to School Rules and Regulations

A study by MANTEP (1995) describes school rules as principles or orders which monitor and guide behavior in a particular school institution. School regulations are official orders that a particular school adopts to ensure proper students' behavior. Mosha (2006) established that school rules and regulations in Tanzania have specific functions including: to prepare pupils as good citizens who become better people in adult life; to make students realize that offenders are punished which will encourage them to obey the laws of the country and to conform to accepted norms and rules of conduct; and to encourage cooperation and harmony in the society.

Some of the school regulations are part and parcel of school rules. School rules are principles or orders which guide behaviour in schools. Some of the rules include being punctual, maintaining neatness and cleanness, living in peace and order, being obedient to teachers, parents and the community, taking care of school materials, equipment and buildings. In principle school rules and

regulations function together to ensure that school rules are maintained for the smooth running of the education institution. Teachers believe that when students are properly disciplined and controlled, there is order, peace and harmony in the school (MANTEP, 1995).

According to Adesina (2002), school rules and rule making can be related to citizenship education. A vital part of education for school rules is an enlightened process for teaching students the norms of citizenship.

Trust

For the purposes of the study relational trust has been defined as the tool that teachers and students used to cultivate interpersonal and social relationships to enhance behaviours and outcomes in schools. Teachers and students developed and nurtured social exchanges as well as the willingness to be vulnerable toward one another's expectations and intentions to create better student outcomes.

Forsyth (2008) argued that trust in school settings has not been widely studied. They further suggested that trust has been studied more from the teacher, parent and administrator perspective.

From a social-behaviour lens, trust has been used to represent social capital networks between people in organisations such as schools (Byrk & Schneider, 2004). Teachers and students spend together a minimum of 180 days per year in schools. At least six hours a day, teachers and students shared teaching and learning experiences, especially in elementary school settings where most hours are spent developing, bonding, and cultivating relationships between teachers and students (Byrk & Schneider, 2004). Evetts (2006) argued that educators need to use their moral compass in order to cultivate relational trust with students. He further argued, while cultivating trust, teachers need to consider other factors such as the student's culture, race, ethnicity, intellectual potential, gender preference, religion, socio-economic and environmental status in order to improve student performance. Therefore, it is important for teachers to compensate for attitudinal biases to develop trusting relationships with students in order to improve student outcomes Forsyth (2008).

As teacher-student relationships formed, a relational learning atmosphere was created and both teachers and students responded to that relational tone set in their classroom. The first relationships formed were at home. As children develop, they learned to transfer their family trust relationships to other adults and peers at school. Schools have represented the place where social capital created social ties between teachers and students to develop trusting relationships (Avoke, 1999).

As social-trust ties increased, more opportunities were created for teachers and students to positively affect student achievement levels (Byrk & Schneider, 2004). School constituents maintained that trusting relationships take time to evolve. Teachers and students experienced varying degrees of trust. When any degree of trust was present, researchers stated that trust flourished and impacted student outcomes (Byrk & Schneider, 2004).

Role Relations and Relational Trust in Schools

Role relations play a part when people try to establish trust. For example, research found when teachers observe each other's classes as critical friends, it implies that a high level of relational trust exists (Byrk & Schneider, 2004). Teachers believe they will benefit from one another over the course of their professional relationship (Byrk & Schneider, 2004). When relational trust builds and becomes a foundation for positive growth, an opportunity is provided for school constituent relationships to flourish and student performance levels to improve (Byrk & Schneider, 2004).

Relational trust between school constituents is composed of integrity. Integrity confirms consistency between what people say and do (Byrk & Schneider, 2004). Application to this concept implies that integrity also highlights moral-ethics based on what people say and do. These behaviours manifest relational trust as a resource for action such as decision-making processes (Byrk & Schneider, 2004). Teachers and students are dependent upon each other, just as principles, parents and teachers are independent upon each other for decision-making strategies. Shared governance acts as a platform to develop trust between teachers and students to improve student.

Academic Honesty

Although the phenomenon of academic honesty amongst students is the subject matter of numerous research, particularly in the United States of America (Passow, et. al. 2006), and although further efforts are used to prevent academic dishonesty in academic assignments (e.g. Mirza & Staples, 2010) in Croatia research and public debate on that topic is very rare. In Croatia, research concerning student cheating in academic assignments (e.g. Hrabak, et. al. 2004) or concerning plagiarism (Pupovac, et. al. 2010) is published in the English language, which does not facilitate public academic debates regarding the problem. Other than the doctoral dissertation of Lidija Bilić-Zulle (2006) examining the prevalence and attitudes towards plagiarism amongst medical students, and a scientific paper of Šimić Šašić and Klarin (2008), who investigated the problem on a sample of secondary school students, there is no other research relating to the mentioned topic written in the Croatian language. What exactly is regarded as dishonest conduct in the educational context? Published works include a number of different descriptions of academic dishonesty amongst pupils and students. McCabe et al. (2001) identified five most common forms of such conduct. Students agree that the most serious form of cheating during an exam is the one that appears during the written part of the test and may include copying answers from another student, using cheat-sheets and helping another student cheat during the exam. Šimić Šašić and Klarin (2008) also observed a high prevalence of such conduct in their research. Other forms of cheating take place during the writing of written assignments (essays, papers, homework) and relate to (according to McCabe, et. al. 2001) plagiarism, fabricating or falsifying bibliography, turning in work done by someone else and copying a few sentences of a material without footnoting them in a paper. Still, Burrus et al. (2007) hold that students might not have an understanding of which behaviours are regarded as cheating (for example, a significantly smaller number of students classify behaviour, such as seeking assistance from a colleague in writing one's homework or studying for an exam from old tests, as dishonest). The experience of the mentioned authors tells us that the ratio of students who learn to recognise cheating during their studies increases after the types of conduct that belong to the category of academically dishonest conduct are clearly defined.

The subject-matter of academic honesty is particularly relevant in our society where the rate of cheating in school and academic assignments is extremely high. In the research conducted by Šimić Šašić and Klarin (2008), 92.71% of high school students in Zadar stated that they had cheated in school once or more than once, while 94% of students of the University of Zagreb – School of Medicine declared they had acted dishonestly in academic assignments at least once during their studies (Hrabak, et. al. 2004), which tells us that such conduct is more of a rule than an exception, and that it is present at all levels of schooling. The crossover of dishonest conduct from the high school to university, and even dishonest conduct at the workplace, was observed in other research (Harding, et. al. 2004; Carpenter, et. al. 2006), as well, reflecting a worrisome impression about the lack of sensibility and tolerance to dishonesty in the educational system, and society as a whole. The research carried out by Šimić Šašić and Klarin (2008), in which pupils who believed that cheating was justifiable and socially acceptable (“everybody does it”) were more likely to cheat in school

assignments, confirms the foregoing. The authors interpret the results by stating that cheating is viewed as a conventional problem (those who are successful in cheating, are actually resourceful), and not a morally questionable one. This conclusion is corroborated by high concordance results on the Perception of Social Injustice Scale, according to which students are most likely to notice that not everyone is equal before law and there is non-acceptance of social values, and general inequality amongst members of society (Šimić Šašić & Klarin, 2008).

Factors Influencing Moral Development

The Family

The family or home seems to be the primary factor in educating and shaping the adolescent's personal development. As Uba (1980) states, the family setting provides nurturance, affection and a variety of opportunities. It is therefore imperative that the person experiences and learns to deal with negative and positive emotions in order to grow psychologically and morally. The experiences of a favourable home environment and a positive emotional climate are critical influences in the person's personality and social development. Consequently, there are certain factors in the adolescent's interaction with the family which are important during early childhood to facilitate optimal development in the person. Accordingly, Maslow's hierarchy of needs emphasizes that basic needs such as food, water, sanitation as well as a sense of belonging, love and care are important factors in the person's development. Clearly, adolescents who receive supportive treatment have a tendency to exhibit smoother patterns of emotional stability and adjustment than youngsters who have been rejected by their parents.

According to World Youth Report (2003) increased mobility and urbanization have reduced the number of opportunities for informal direct communication between the family and other social institutions including schools, churches and agencies of local government. However, such communication is more likely to occur in small towns and cities with relatively stable populations. Torbet (1996) mentions that the family functions as a system of interaction and the way it conducts personal relationships has a very powerful effect on the psychosocial development of people. Within the family, every individual has a basic need for security which is satisfied through belonging. Everyone needs to know where and how he fits in. The family setting enables people to develop the skills by which they can enter new groups and find a place for themselves. Significantly, the family is the first and most important socializing agency. This is where young people first begin to understand how human beings relate to each other. A young person has no basis for comparison because he or she observes human relationships in the family first. Ideally, the family should be the place in which a young person can feel unqualified acceptance. In contrast, when members of the family are continuously prompting a young person to change or to improve, their sense of security is affected.

Parents can also hinder the development of learners by giving them more attention than is necessary for healthy development. Smooth love prevents the adolescent from assuming responsibility and this is detrimental. On the other hand, parents sometimes choose the adolescent's friends or hinder him from making any social contacts outside of the family. Unwittingly, parents sometimes hinder the social development of the adolescent in subtle ways. According to Stewart (2010) report that among adolescent boys from equally disadvantaged backgrounds, the more knife fights the individual has witnessed, the more likely he is to carry a knife and use it. Unfortunately, this is also evident in families where violence is practiced by parents, so do adolescents emulate violent behaviour which subsequently manifests itself in the school environment.

The School

The school is also an important factor that influences moral development. Erickson (1950) notes that the school exists in communities and characteristics of communities, urban versus rural or tightly knit versus impersonal influence the ways in which schools are organized and operate. According to Feldman (2002) the school acts as an agent of society in that it is organized to perpetuate society's knowledge, skills, customs and beliefs. School can serve as a fulfilling role for social activities and as a powerful agency of socialization where cultural values and norms that have been adhered to and treasured for years and years are formally transmitted to the young and growing generations.

According to Oladele (1998), one of the purposes of the school is to extend the socialization process begun by the family. Furthermore, at school, an adolescent is expected to relate to a new form of authority, namely teachers, to follow a new set of rules, to make new friends and to learn to get along with adolescents who are not his or her friends. Accordingly, the teacher is noted as an important figure that applies new rules and makes demands which differ from those of the adolescent's parents. New behaviour patterns must consequently be learnt and they are very different from the behaviour patterns the adolescent has known up to then. In contrast, adolescents who are emotionally secure, who have gained a reasonable amount of preschool social experience, who have developed some independence from their parents differ from the ones who are still unsure of themselves and who have had little social experience outside the home.

According to Pekauskys, (2000) all schools have rules. If learning is to take place, adolescents cannot interfere with one another or with the teacher. As a result, adolescents must respect and cooperate with each other and when differences do arise, they must learn to compromise. Supposedly, teachers are important role models for values such as honesty, compassion, altruism and justice. Therefore, adolescents should further be instructed by parents and teachers alike in the practical implementation of their moral value systems. Furthermore, adolescents should be given the opportunity to make independent and responsible choices concerning moral values.

Peers

The peers during adolescence become more differentiated, influential and provide powerful social rewards in terms of status, prestige, friendship, popularity and acceptance. However, the peer system also can assert a powerful negative influence by encouraging or rewarding detrimental behaviour such as cheating, stealing, smoking, using a gun, drinking, drug abuse and irresponsible sex. Peers are also prominent in the microsystem of learners. Better peer relations are associated with better academic motivation and performance. For example, good students are more likely to have supportive peers than weaker students (Levitt, Guacci-Franco and Levitt, 1994). Furthermore, an adolescent relationship with friends is of a different kind than that experienced within the family unit.

Playing of games is one of the most common experiences of social interaction amongst peers. Games give young people a chance to use power as leaders or captains. Certainly, young people's participation in many different games continues to be an important agent in the socialization process. On the contrary, an adolescent with little social success develops a negative self-image, which negatively affects his or her cognitive growth. As a matter of fact, young people who begin school with more confidence and are warm and secure in their relationship with their families continue to build positive relationships with peers and other adults outside the family sphere.

Piaget (1965) mention that adolescents also become more dependent on peer relations than younger people as their ties to parents become looser and they gain greater independence especially in the early years of adolescence, dependent yearnings exist alongside independent strivings, hostility is mixed with love and conflicts occur over cultural values and social behaviour. Piaget (1970) also suggests that moral development is influenced by cognitive disequilibrium and by experiences of cooperation with peers.

According to Uba (1980), peer relationships are an integral part of emotional development and social stability in adolescents. Furthermore, the general level of success, emotional and social contentment, achieved by an adolescent can be dependent upon the number and quality of their peer relationships. Peer interaction can be a positive influence when it echoes the aptitudes and desirable characteristics of an adolescent. Furthermore, those relationships that are assessed as high caliber will endow self-esteem escalation and optimistic growth. As a result, perceptions of relationship quality are important with regard to causing positive or negative developmental outcomes.

Television

According to Lefton (2000) television should be considered as a socializing agent because it reveals many aspects of the society and elicits cognitive processes in learners that affect their understanding of the world. Essentially, television also depicts relationships between people in various settings, thus providing adolescents with models of how to behave or interact at similar situations which influence moral behaviour.

Television has proved to be a powerful educational tool for adolescents in this modern era whether for positive or negative influence. According to Feldman (2000) the media including, television access among many adolescents, provides additional unique and significant socializing experiences that cannot be underestimated. These can even contribute to improved literacy levels. Educational and religious programmes can provide adolescents with access to novel moral information and they are also capable of creating and promoting their moral beliefs and actions to others. Berns (2004) mentions that adolescents acquire attitudes, emotional responses and new styles of conduct through filmed and televised modeling. In addition, Lewon (2010) state that television is quite different for the following reasons, namely; domesticity, it penetrates into the ordinary life of family and household; in terms of continuity, it provides an endless daily programme rather than a once off entertainment; immediacy-wise, it makes people communicate events to an unlimited audience as they happen; for variable usage, it can be used in various ways. Some television programmes generate crime, promiscuous sexual behaviour and violence quintessentially. Therefore, adolescents of today are exposed, through the media and their peers, to a vast array of issues dealing with violence, sexuality and substance abuse. Long You (2004) advise that parents should encourage discussing issues openly with their children to share concerns or correct misconceptions.

Violence can also influence learners in a negative way. Public concern over values portrayed by television that are in conflict with values transmitted by parents include sex where television and movies present sex on a physical level, both visually and verbally; violence where adolescents are exposed to too much violence.

Internet

In recent times, people live in a technology driven world. Some adolescents have familiarized themselves with the internet which set a bad example of moral values and behaviours. These wrong values and morals are emulated by some adolescents. Technically, most adolescents can browse

through lot of search engines to search for wrong educational programmes where even pornography is explored. Many adolescents are clued up with advanced internet searches. As a social context, the internet enables multiple communication functions, such as email, instant messaging, chat and blogs to allow adolescent to participate and co-construct their own environments Louw and Louw and Louw (2007). According to de Kant (2000) young people are enthusiastic about the internet because, more than any other medium, it helps them establish contact with the outside world and freely seek information.

Jenkins (2004) contends that the use of the internet for surfing, games, chat rooms and similar activities has grown and continued to grow enormously in the past few years. In comparison, this development is a world-wide phenomenon which equally parallels the rapid advent of television in the 1950's. Undoubtedly, the use of the internet poses very similar problems to those of all other media, they can be used for informative, educational ends, they can be purely for recreational purposes and they can be used in ways that may cause concern such as incorporating violence and pornography which affect moral development of people. According to Kante (2000) teenagers use the internet more hours than adults. Similar to the television, regardless of age, greater internet use predicted a drop in time spent communicating with family members and in size of nearby and distant social networks.

On a positive note, Kail and Cavanaugh (2000), mention that the possibilities of people to present themselves in varying ways through the appropriate use of narratives have escalated with the growth of the internet. With the internet base, communication has increased greatly.

Consequences of the Lack of Moral Development in Schools

Drug Abuse

According to Aina (1998) drugs are any substances which can be of natural or synthetic origin, whose introduction into the body can cause modifications or several complications. Drug abuse refers to a disorder characterized by a destructive pattern of using these substances that lead to significant problems and distress. It can also be described as the taking of a psychoactive drug or performance enhancing drug for a non-therapeutic or non-medical effect. In short, drug abuse is the uncontrolled and illegal consumption of drugs.

Hannah, et. al. (2017), refers to drug abuse as the production, distribution and consumption of outlawed drugs. Most of these illegal drugs are harmful to humans and animals. Drug abuse is a worldwide phenomenon. The practice is on the increase especially in Africa and Latin America. It is a source of income for traders, but has devastating effects on consumers. Harmful drugs appear on two forms: their original forms and the transformed forms. In that original state, these drugs include grass, leaves, roots or barks of trees. Drugs on their transformed state could be in the form of tablets, capsules, powder or liquid. These outlawed drugs include marijuana, opium, cocaine and cigarette.

Vandalism

Vandalism is an act that relate to the deliberate violation of school learners/boarders and staff property on school and hostel premises, such as the deliberate breaking of windows, graffiti on school walls, scratching and breaking of school desks, tearing of school textbooks, breaking of toilet seats, taps, mirrors, and the stealing of others' property, just to mention these few. vandalism as a concept comes from the uncivilized barbarians of Roman times who willfully and maliciously destroyed, or harmed public or private property (De wet 2004).

Various disciplines such as psychology and sociology have examined vandalism and different perspectives, and it is difficult to reach consensus on a definition. Nevertheless, some of the definitions have common elements, such as, an intentional act aimed at damaging or destroying an object that is another's property, a voluntary degradation of the environment with no profit motive

whatsoever, the results of which are considered damage by the actor(s) as well as the victim in relation to the norms that govern the situation and the willful or malicious destruction, injury, disfigurement, or defacement of property without the consent of the owner (Conoley 2004) Most of the definitions highlight intentionality, destructiveness, and property ownership. This form of destructive behaviour is thus motivated not by profit but by other factors. De Wet (2004) suggests that acts of vandalism are motivated by anger, boredom.

The criminal actions of vandals which included looting of computer equipment, defacing of walls, destruction of furniture, painting of graffiti, and burning of classrooms is a most heinous and despicable act of cowardice and mental derangement (Diez, 2010).

Examination Fraud (Malpractice)

Examination, an integral part of the teaching and learning process, has been used for ages as a means of ascertaining the status of achievement of individual learners. However, for some time now, some individuals have avoided the rigours of study and instead depended on fraudulent means to pass examination by indulging in examination malpractices thereby distorting its validity and reliability Uzocukwa (2015).

In order to ensure that examinations possess transparency, integrity, validity and reliability, they are guided by a code of ethics, which is translated into rules and regulations. Thus any unethical action leading to the flouting of these rules and regulations, whether committed before, during or after an examination, constitutes examination malpractice (Uzocukwa, 2015). Ojerinde (2006), views examination malpractice as any act of wrong doing, which gives a candidate undue advantage over others in obtaining success in an examination and which tends to jeopardise the credibility of the certificates issued. Aigbekaen (2006), describes examination malpractice as a hydro-headed phenomenon, which occurs when an individual abandons the rigours of studying and depends instead on fraudulent means to pass examinations, leading to a distortion in the assessment of students' academic performance. The perpetrators of this deadly virus in our educational system, according to Eriba (2012), include students, even in nursery schools either, single – handedly or in collaboration with other students, teachers, invigilators, supervisors, parents, whole communities, examination officials, printers and other mercenaries. Hannah, et. al. (2017), defines examination fraud as an offense committed by learners or candidates or officials, who choose to use dubious or unorthodox means to succeed in examinations or influence examination results.

Research Methodology

This study made use of the mixed sequential explanatory design, that is two consecutive phases within the same study. Therefore, the quantitative data were collected first and analysed, then followed by the collection and analysis of qualitative findings. The qualitative data were then used to back the quantitative data. The accessible population was comprised of 301Citizenship Education teachers drawn from three divisions namely Fako, Meme and Manyu, from where a sample of 143 Citizenship Education teachers was selected. Three sampling techniques were used in this study namely the stratified sampling, purposive sampling and the simple random sampling techniques. The study made use of a questionnaire and an interview guide to respectively collect quantitative and qualitative data. Instruments were validated through two phases, the face and content validity while the reliability coefficient stood at0.763, more than the accepted 0.70Cronbach Alpha's level. The Direct Delivery Technique (DDT) was used in administering the instruments. Structured items were analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) version 24.0, interviews were analysed thematically, while hypotheses were tested through inferential statistics using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation.

FINDINGS

Research Question: To what extent does professional development of Citizenship Education teachers influence the moral development of students?

Table 1

Frequency table of teachers responses on professional Development

SN	Item	SA	A	D	SD	Total	Agree	Disagree
1	I carry out research in Citizenship Education.	90 (63%)	29 (20%)	20 (14%)	4 (3%)	143 (100%)	119 (83%)	24 (17%)
2	I attend workshops on Citizenship Education.	72 (50%)	47 (33%)	22 (15%)	2 (1%)	143 (100%)	119 (83%)	24 (17%)
3	More experienced colleagues' mentor junior colleagues in the teaching of Citizenship Education.	60 (42%)	57 (40%)	22 (15%)	4 (3%)	143 (100%)	117 (82%)	26 (18%)
4	I visit resource centers/libraries to read extensively on Citizenship Education.	66 (46%)	38 (27%)	35 (24%)	4 (3%)	143 (100%)	104 (73%)	39 (27%)
5	Attestations are given to teachers who have attended seminars on Citizenship Education	45 (31%)	34 (24%)	46 (32%)	18 (13%)	143 (100%)	79 (55%)	64 (45%)
6	I have been trained in selecting and using the most appropriate instructional materials for the teaching of Citizenship Education.	27 (19%)	14 (10%)	59 (41%)	43 (30%)	143 (100%)	41 (29%)	102 (71%)
Total		360 (42%)	219 (26%)	204 (24%)	75 (9%)	858 (100%)	579 (67%)	279 (33%)

It was agreed by the majority of teachers that teachers of Citizenship Education undergo professional development, thus professional development of teachers influences the moral development of students (67%). This trend was still very high for five out of six components of this indicator except for the fifth component. This therefore indicates that professional development of teachers has an influence on the moral development of students (table 1).

Research Hypothesis Ho: There is no significant relationship between Professional Development of Teachers in Citizenship Education and Moral Development of Students in Secondary Schools. The results from the analysis are presented on table 2.

Table 2

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis of the Relationship between Professional Development of Teachers in Citizenship Education and Moral Development of Students (N=143)

Variables	$\sum X$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum XY$	r_{xy}	P-value
Professional development	1710	21562	22297	0.120	0.151
Moral development	1854	25060			

P-value* <0.05, d.f. = 141, Critical r_{xy} = 0.159

Table 2 presents the relationship between the professional development of teachers and students' moral development. As noticed on the table 2, the correlation coefficient is 0.120 indicating a positive relationship between teachers' professional development and students' moral development. This implies that as the teachers' professional development increases the students' moral development improves. However, the relationship was not statistically significant given that the p-value of 0.151 is greater than the threshold value of 0.05 ($0.151 > 0.05$). The calculated correlation coefficient also is less than the critical value ($0.120 < 0.159$) at the 0.05 level of significance.

Consequently, the null hypothesis was retained, meaning that there is no significant relationship between professional development of teachers in Citizenship Education and moral development of students in secondary schools.

Qualitative Findings on Teachers' Professional Development

Qualitative findings from interviews with teachers on their professional development were analysed thematically and the different ways through which professional development is carried out by citizenship education teachers are grouped and presented below with some quotations.

Workshops: Participants held that workshops are used to better their professional development. One participant said workshops are usually organized, another said they use School workshops and one also said some regional workshops are organized.

Seminars: They equally identified seminars as being useful. A participant said they use internal seminars, another said Regional seminars and one talked about using departmental seminars.

Peer mentorship: This was also pointed out as a participant said it is done by peer mentorship, one held that senior colleagues help junior ones and another said Heads of department mentor others.

Findings through interviews with teachers on how professional development helps teachers of citizenship education in molding students' behaviour were thematically analysed as follows:
Better teaching: It was established that professional development makes teaching better. Different participants said it equips teachers with good teaching methods, improves teaching using the competency based approach, and makes the teaching process easier.

Good moral value: That it enables teachers to pass on good moral values to learners. A participant said it helps me to transmit good moral values to students, one said I develop positive student-teacher relationship.

Subject mastery: A teacher said it enables teachers to master the subject, one said I learn the objectives of the subject well and another said it gives a deeper view of the subject.

Evaluation of students: They held that it makes evaluation better as a teacher said it helps me in evaluating students' behavior, one held that it prepares teachers on question setting and another said it guides teachers in selecting questions.

Discipline: Participants supported that it improves their ability to discipline students as they said it teaches me how to discipline students, it improves my classroom management, and that it provides me with classroom techniques.

In a nutshell, teachers of Citizenship Education to a greater extent carry out professional development exercises and that this professional development helps teachers of citizenship education in molding students' behavior. All the same it was proven that there is no significant relationship between

professional development of teachers in Citizenship Education and moral development of students in secondary schools.

Discussion

The findings revealed that there is no significant relationship between teachers' professional development and students' moral development, though there is a relationship. This implies that as the teachers' professional development increases the students' moral development improves. However, the relationship was not statistically significant, therefore, the null hypothesis was retained and the alternative hypothesis rejected. The fact that a wide range of teachers from different subject areas as revealed by the demographic information teach Citizenship Education tells us that the teachers' areas of specialization have no significant impact on the moral development of students.

These findings are backed by Malvis (2010), who carried out a study in social studies teachers' perceptions and practices of educating citizens in a democracy in secondary schools in Botswana and revealed a gloomy picture on Citizenship Education as perceived, interpreted and enacted within secondary schools investigated hence leading to the conclusion that Citizenship Education for Moral Development remains an illusion rather than a reality. He also found that teachers conceptualize Citizenship Education in multiple ways indicating that Citizenship in Botswana is complex, fluid and not homogenous.

The findings are also backed by the Theory of Reconstructionism by Nziramasanga (1999) which holds that every society is in need of constant reconstruction; that to reconstruct is to do something again to make it better which constitutes the foundation for social change within a dynamic context and involves a reconstruction of education in the process of improving a society.

Qualitative information gathered from interviews with teachers revealed that the professional development of Citizenship Education is mostly carried out through seminars, workshops and peer mentorship. It was also made known that professional development equips the teacher with the right teaching methods, develops their skills in question setting, use of instructional materials, development of good student-teacher relationships and students' discipline.

Conclusion

The importance of moral development in the life of every individual cannot be over emphasized, given the fact that morality is the driving force of every society. Through the teaching of Citizenship Education in schools morality can be inculcated in the citizens. Therefore it will be very important that the teaching of Citizenship Education in secondary schools be improved in order to better the moral development of the citizens as this will go a long way in making the society a better place to live in. The study concluded that professional development has an influence on moral development though the relationship is not significant. It therefore implies that an improvement on the professional development of teachers will better the moral development of students. The study therefore suggested that the Cameroon government could include the department of Citizenship Education in her teacher training schools to ensure the training of teachers specifically for Citizenship Education and those regional delegations of Education should increase the number of regional and divisional seminars/workshops for Citizenship Education teachers.

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